

PAES-25: Local Search, Archiving and Multi/Many-objective Pseudo-Boolean Functions

— Supplementary material —

Joshua Knowles and Arnaud Liefoghe

¹ SLB, Cambridge, Cambridgeshire, UK

² LISIC, Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale, Calais, France

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This document contains supplementary material to the main paper. It reports detailed and additional experimental results obtained with several alternative variants of PAES-25. The experiments were conducted on the following benchmark functions:

- LOTZ (Leading Ones Trailing Zeros) with 2 objectives,
- LITZ (Leading Integers Trailing Zeros) with 4 and 8 objectives,
- sLITZ (shuffled LITZ) with 4 and 8 objectives,
- FRITZ (First Run of Integers Trailing Zeros) with 4 and 8 objectives.

The following statistics are reported — all being plotted over time:

- the relative deviation of the current archive from the PF in terms of hypervolume (lower is better, with 0 indicating the PF is reached),
- the archive size,
- the number and proportion of encountered Pareto-optimal points,
- the proportion of Pareto-optimal points in the current archive,
- the number of accepted moves,
- the last accepted move,
- the sum of objectives from the current solution.

Fig. 1. Impact of the bounded archiver on relative hypervolume deviation over time for LOTZ (2 objectives).

Fig. 2. Impact of the archiver (and bound), mutation operator and acceptance rule on relative hypervolume deviation over time for 2 and 4 objectives.

Fig. 3. Archive size over time for 2 and 4 objectives.

Fig. 4. Number of Pareto-optimal points seen over time for 2 and 4 objectives.

Fig. 5. Proportion of Pareto-optimal points seen over time for 2 and 4 objectives.

Fig. 6. Proportion of Pareto-optimal points in current archive for 2 and 4 objectives.

Fig. 7. Number of accepted moves over time for 2 and 4 objectives.

Fig. 8. Last accepted moves over time for 2 and 4 objectives.

Fig. 9. Sum of objectives from current solution for 2 and 4 objectives.

Fig. 10. Archive size over time for 8 objectives.

Fig. 11. Number of Pareto-optimal points seen over time for 8 objectives.

Fig. 12. Proportion of Pareto-optimal points seen over time for 8 objectives.

Fig. 13. Proportion of Pareto-optimal points in current archive for 8 objectives.

Fig. 14. Number of accepted moves over time for 8 objectives.

Fig. 15. Last accepted moves over time for 8 objectives.

Fig. 16. Sum of objectives from current solution for 8 objectives.

Fig. 17. Evolution of the current solution in example runs with selected algorithm settings for LOTZ (2 objectives).

Fig. 18. Evolution of the current solution in example runs with selected algorithm settings for FRITZ with 4 objectives.